

NEOLOGISMS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of nominative processes and lexical changes occurring at the present stage of development of the English language. It is the lexical system of the language, being the most flexible and mobile, that is constantly changing along with the development of the language community, enriching itself with new lexical units and reflecting current social trends. New words that have appeared in the language in the last few years have become the object of study of this article.

A brief review of theoretical approaches to the problem of studying neologisms and the factors influencing their occurrence is accompanied by a comparison of the statistical data of linguists of the late 20th and early 21st centuries. The paper considers the specificity of popular neologisms of the English language and their actualization in everyday communication of native speakers.

Keywords: *neologism, language development, language changes, language picture of the world.*

INTRODUCTION

Language, like any living organism, is constantly evolving, enriching itself with a variety of linguistic means. The most mobile and flexible is, as you know, the lexical system of the language, which changes dynamically and constantly along with the development of a particular language community, reflecting the changes taking place

in society and modern trends. This article is devoted to the lexical metamorphoses of the English language that have taken place in the last few years and the attitude of native speakers themselves towards them.

It should be said that the field of neology, which has attracted the attention of linguists for more than a decade, is now developing as rapidly as the object of its study itself - new words. And if at the end of the twentieth century, researchers estimated the number of new English words in the range of 12,000 per year, then in 2002 this figure, according to some estimates, increased to 10,000 new words and word forms per day. Quantity the neologisms that arise in the language every day in our time are no longer calculable. Of course, not all of these words are included in a wide range of usage and fall into dictionaries. Nevertheless, lexicographers are trying to capture all the new lexical units that appear, which makes it possible to draw a more complete picture of the current trends in the development of the language and the society that speaks it.

A large number of works and studies are devoted to the study and analysis of neologisms, which consider new words from different sides and aspects. The very specificity of the object under study is such that the topic does not exhaust itself, and research work continues to be relevant, supplementing and clarifying the analyzed phenomenon.

INTERPRETATION OF THE CONCEPT "NEOLOGISM"

First of all, let us define the concept itself, which we will use in this article. So, in the most general sense, words or meanings of existing words that appeared in the language relatively recently are considered neologisms in the lexicon. Irina Rets, having studied the possible approaches of researchers to the interpretation of the term "neologism", which vary depending on the research goals, identifies 5 main theoretical approaches: stylistic, denotative, structural, etymological and lexicographic. Within the framework of the stylistic approach, neologism is treated as a word, the novelty of which is marked by its new stylistic use, an example of which can be words passing from jargon or metalanguage into everyday language (for example, the term downtime

'time when one is not working or active'). The denotative theory considers neologisms as words that arise to name new objects and concepts and thus acquire new denotative meanings, such as smartphone, selfie, e-book. The structural approach defines neologisms as words that have a completely new linguistic and acoustic form and structure, such as: Tolkien's hobbit. In the etymological approach, neologism is understood as a word that already exists in the language and has developed a new meaning: umbrella 1) 'device used as protection against rain'; 2) 'a protecting force or influence'. And, finally, supporters of the lexicographic approach to neologism invest in this concept, among other things, the fact that a new word is not recorded in dictionaries, for example, the language unit cinematherapy 'using films as therapeutic tools', which scored 70,000 citations in the Google search engine , but has not yet been reflected in lexicographic publications.

Summarizing these approaches, we can conclude that even the novelty factor common to all definitions seems to be ambiguous and in many respects contradictory, since the researcher must determine for himself whether this or that linguistic unit is new for all members of society or only for a certain - for the native part of native speakers, for the language of everyday communication or only for a certain sublanguage, metalanguage, etc.

In this work, neologisms will be understood as words or phrases that are new in their form and meaning at the current time and have a new socio-cultural meaning. In other words, to neologisms we will rank both the actual new words in form and meaning, and the units already available in the nominative fund, the meaning of which has been transformed due to a change in discursive reference.

CONCLUSION

Summing up the reasoning about the reasons for the "success" or "failure" of certain neologisms of the English language, we note that language processes are taking place rapidly in comparison with past periods, within a few days there are as many new words as in other times appeared over the course of several years. The language in our time lives as if in a fast motion. And if the language is a reflection of the life of the people, and the vocabulary is a kind of litmus test for social and cultural changes, then it can be assumed that new words, no matter how unusual and ridiculous they may seem to most of society at the beginning, appear and become popular not by chance. Their appearance is natural, as they bring new ideas and values with them.

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